

Flexcrash

D6.2 Data Management Plan (first version)

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Revision History

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0.1	01/02/2023	Simona Neri (EUT)	Draft version circulated to partners together with the questionnaire
1.0	18/02/2023	Begoña Casas (EUT)	Revision
2.0	23/02/2023	Simona Neri (EUT)	Format revision and Submission

Executive Summary

The report deals with the set-up of the internal guidelines that dictate the rules to collect, process and generate data. It will provide the project strategy on data sharing, curation and compliance to FAIR policy.

This deliverable has been created by Project coordinator Simona Neri with the support of the technical coordinator Begoña Casas and the proposal and project coordination Department based on common best coordination practices in Eurecat that has served as a common tool kit reference for H2020 projects and have continuity in Horizon Europe projects coordinated by this entity. Some sections concerning the management of Horizon Europe projects that are common to other similar have been directly taken from Eurecat internal Project Handbook text.

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Terminology and Acronyms

<i>DMP</i>	<i>Data Management Plan</i>
<i>OA</i>	<i>Open Access</i>
<i>FAIR</i>	<i>Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable</i>
<i>AVFF</i>	<i>Adding value functional features</i>

1. Introduction

The Data Management Plan is a critical task in every Horizon Europe project. It is an important building block for the dissemination of results and, thus, the impact of the project. The DMP needs to be updated over the course of the project whenever significant changes arise, such as (but not limited to):

- new data
- changes in consortium policies (e.g. new innovation potential, decision to file for a patent)
- changes in consortium composition and external factors (e.g. new consortium members joining or old members leaving).

The DMP should be updated as a minimum in time with the periodic evaluation/assessment of the project and as foreseen within the grant agreement such an update needs will be provided in Aug 2026. Furthermore, the consortium can define an internal timetable for review in the DMP itself.

This document is meant to facilitate the task of collecting partner's input relevant to the DMP.

Section 2 provides definitions and examples of each of the columns needed to fill in the section 3.

Section 3 provides the template for partners to insert their contributions. It has five headlines, all of which must be completed with relevant and accurate information, with as much details as possible.

Note: Not all questions might fit with all partners. In case you fill some aspects do not apply to your organisation, please explicitly declare N/A.

For further guidance, please consult [Guidelines on FAIR Data Management](#).

Flexcrash believes in Open Science and Open Data as a mechanism to bring society a return of investment from our research. The Data Management is addressed in parallel with the coordination of the project in T6.2 and will be continuously update during the project implementation. The FAIR Data Management guidelines, Rules on the Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Data Access to Research Data in H2020 and the guidelines established for data management in Horizon Europe will be complied. The plan will include: (i) the handling of research data during and after the end of the project; (ii) what data will be collected, processed, and generated; (iii) which methodology and standards will be applied; (iv) whether data will be shared/made open access, and; (v) how data will be curated and preserved (including after the project).

Furthermore, Flexcrash might be in need to apply OA restrictions over some data. These restrictions, which will be assessed and be handled by the appointed Data Manager, may come from:

- Confidentiality and IP protection to certain deliverables, datasets and outputs (e.g., underlying algorithmic and methods susceptible to being patented).
- Any sensitive or personal data collected during the project (e.g., contact leads in dissemination activities, etc.,) will be dealt with in compliance with Directive 95/46/EC

and GDPR Regulation 2016/679), considering consent, breach notification, right to access and right to be forgotten.

- Protection of imported rights of pre-existent, non-public datasets (e.g., IP rights applicable to dissemination materials).

The DMP will further elaborate on the draft table of data generated provided in the table below and will analyse in detail the relation of each dataset with the project exploitable outputs to gain a clear understanding of the limitations of the OA rule, if applicable, and its impact in the exploitation and dissemination strategies. For the DMP, Flexcrash will collect and/or generate 4 categories of data that are further detailed in the next sections by each Partner.

Research data and metadata: datasets resulting from research and materials and manufacturing processes; metadata and configuration files; bug logs and feedback logs; developer internal documentation; market research.

Computer software: including software applications in binary form, libraries in the form of SDKs, plugins and respective source code.

Data for evaluation: consists of materials or datasets generated or collected by the project for evaluation purposes.

Documents and dissemination materials: Includes deliverables, reports, demonstrations, dissemination and communication.

Flexcrash deals hybrid manufacturing using aluminium alloys to produce vehicle parts to address the crash optimization efforts, the front-end, as the most effective approach to reduce weight and optimize the crash performance of current and future vehicles. Materials and manufacturing solutions will be developed and characterized using advanced testing and modelling methodologies.

From here, the main data categories areas come from the laboratory tests and software simulations such as:

- Material characterisation data
- Full crash results
- Crash Performance Validation
- L-DED process parameters
- testing performance of a antiintrusion lateral door cross bar adopting the concept of AVFF
- AVFF elementary pattern virtual characterization in flexural
- AVFF elementary pattern virtual characterization of mechanical behaviour included crashworthiness
- Validation experiment data
- A Curated Set of Mixed-Traffic Critical Scenarios
- Model input files

Furthermore, the project intends to exploit y disseminate the main achievements in order to reach potential customers, investor or stakeholders interested in the developments.

During these activities various data will be collected, like among others:

- Project Social Media statistics
- Project website analytics
- Project newsletter subscriptions
- Project data from dissemination and communication activities
- Project data from media outlets / journalists
- Project personal data collected for project events (registrations /attendees)
- Exploitable Results

2. Data items

2.1 [Data Summary](#)

- State the purpose of the data collection/generation
- Explain the relation to the objectives of the project
- Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected
- Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)
- Specify the origin of the data
- State the expected size of the data (if known)
- Outline the data utility: to whom it will be useful

Examples of data generation:

Observational. Data captured in real time, usually unique and irreplaceable e.g., foodborne surveillance.

Experimental. Data from experimental results, e.g., from lab equipment, often reproducible, but can be expensive.

Simulation. Data generated from test models where model and metadata may be more important than output data from the model.

Derived or compiled. Data, resulting from processing or combining 'raw' data, often reproducible but expensive e.g., compiled databases, text mining, aggregate census data.

Reference or canonical. Data (static or organic), conglomeration or collection of smaller (peer reviewed) datasets, most probably published and curated.

Examples of types of data:

images, audio, video, textual, tabular, numerical measurements, survey responses, focus group and individual interview transcripts, economic indicators, demographics, opinion polling, measurements generated by sensors/laboratory instruments, computer modelling, simulations, observations and/or field studies, specimen, etc.

2.1.1 [Making data findable](#)

- Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision)
- Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?

- Outline naming conventions used
- Outline the approach towards search keyword
- Outline the approach for clear versioning
- Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what type of metadata will be created and how

Recommendations for naming and labelling criteria:

- **Organization:** consider the file naming constraints of the system where the file is located
- **Context:** include content specific or descriptive information, independent of where the data are stored.
- **Consistency:** choose a naming convention and ensure that the rules are followed systematically by always including the same information (such as date and time) in the same order (e.g., YYYYMMDD)

Metadata standards: [Metadata Standards Directory](#)

2.1.2 Making data openly accessible

- Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so.
- Specify how the data will be made available
- Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?
- Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited
- Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions

2.1.3 Making data interoperable

- Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability.
- Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

Example data formats: *Text Plain text file (TXT), Flat files (EMBL), MS Word (DOC, DOCX), Portable Document Format (PDF), Rich Text Format (RTF), Hyper-Text Markup Language (HTML), Extensible Markup Language (XML) Numerical SPSS, Stata, MS Excel, SAS, Flat files, fixed field format files, delimited files, Hierarchical files Multimedia JPEG, TIFF, GIF, Dicom, MPEG, Quicktime, Bitmap, PNG Models 3D, Statistical, Similitude, Macroeconomic, Causal Software Java, C, Perl, Python, Ruby, PHP, Discipline Specific formats (which ones?)*

Example: [DataCite Metadata Schema](#) and [generator](#)

2.1.4 [Increase data re-use](#)

- Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible
- Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed
- Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why
- Describe data quality assurance processes
- Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

2.2 [Allocation of resources](#)

- Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs
- Describe costs and potential value of long-term preservation
- Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project

2.3 [Data security](#)

- Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data: What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)? Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?

2.4 [Ethical aspects](#)

- To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former
 - Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
 - Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

2.5 [Other Issues](#)

- Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any).
- Intellectual Property Rights issues?
- Anonymization or transformation of confidential or sensitive data

- Aggregation: the combination of related categories, usually within a common branch of a hierarchy, to provide information at a broader level to that at which detailed observations are taken.
- Anonymization: cases are stripped of revealing identifiers such as name and address. Pseudo anonymization is a common technique for protecting identities in qualitative data.
- Perturbation: a deliberate distortion is introduced at the level of tabular data cells. e.g., Population Census data are sometimes released with perturbations as a trade-off for geographical detail.

3. DMP table and questions to be completed by Partners

3.1 Fair Data Management

1.Relevant partner:	Data set name:	Dataset description:	4.Dataset type: primary or secondary?	Data source:	Work Package / Relevant Task:	If it is a new dataset, when will it be available? If it's an existing dataset when was it collected? e.g., 2023; after the FLEXCRASH traffic simulation,	What is the purpose of data collection/generation? "Data utility": to whom this dataset will be useful? In which Work Package / Task will it be used?	Relation to project Asset(s) –
Míriam Vendrell - Eurecat - miriam.vendrell@eurecat.org	Project Social Media statistics	Twitter Analytics LinkedIn analytics for tracking the number of followers likes, shares and monitor KPIs.	Primary	Twitter & LinkedIn Analytics	WP5 - T5.2	During all the project's execution (M1 - M48)	Showcase the impact and visibility of the project through Social Media networks	
Míriam Vendrell - Eurecat miriam.vendrell@eurecat.org	Project website analytics	Website data in terms of traffic (visits, pages viewed, users, time on page, etc.). Subscriptions will be possible through Mailchimp sign up form. Data is closed to EURECAT due to GDPR	Primary	Matomo	WP5 - Task 5.2	From the creation of project website (M3) until the end of the project	To know the visibility of the project's website (from which countries we receive more visitors, number of visits, number of page views, number of users, number of actions per visit, etc.)	

		as it includes personal data.						
Miriam Vendrell - Eurecat - miriam.vendrell@eurecat.org	Project newsletter subscriptions	Personal data of Flexcrash newsletter subscribers for the production of e-mail campaigns and newsletters distribution.	Primary	Mailchimp	WP5 - Task 5.2	During all the project's execution	Identify and have a list of subscribers to send project's newsletters or other direct communications	

<p>Miriam Vendrell - Eurecat - miriam.vendrell@eurecat.org</p>	<p>Project data from dissemination and communication activities</p>	<p>This data will be collected through a periodic monitoring of the project's miscellaneous dissemination activities such as publications in relevant journals, social media posts, participation to conferences and events, etc. The data will consist of a list of dissemination and communication activities done by partners for a specific period. The purpose of collecting this data is to assess the outreach and efficiency of the dissemination activities during the implementation of the project. Data will be collected from partners through Excel file. Data will be open to Flexcrash partners during the project execution.</p>	<p>Primary</p>	<p>Data will be collected from partners through Excel file.</p>	<p>WP5 - Task 5.2</p>	<p>During all the project's execution</p>	<p>The purpose of collecting this data is to assess the outreach and efficiency of the dissemination activities during the implementation of the project.</p>	
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Míriam Vendrell - Eurecat - miriam.vendrell@eurecat.org	Project data from media outlets / journalists	A file with personal data for journalists and media outlets of interest will be created by EUT by filtering their media database.	Primary	EUT internal database	WP5 - Task 5.2	Available from the beginning of the project	The database will be used for sending Flexcrash press releases to the media and pithing project results	
Míriam Vendrell - Eurecat - miriam.vendrell@eurecat.org	Project personal data collected for project events (registrations / attendees)	Dataset on personal details of attendants / registrants to the stakeholder engagement events organized by Flexcrash.	Primary	There is no data source, Formassembly will be used as data processor.	WP5 - Task 5.2	Available from the first event organised	Participants lists to manage their participation into project events.	
Natàlia Carmona, Eurecat, natalia.carmona@eurecat.org	Exploitable Results	List of exploitable results considering its category, target users, added value, exploitation route, IPR mechanism, ownership and contact partner	Primary	Data provided by partners	All	The data has been collected preliminary and will be updated throughout the project	Exploitation magement	
Alessio Tommasi, GEM, alessio.tommasi@gemmate-technologies.com	AVFF elementary pattern virtual characterization in flexural	data about flexural behaviour of elementary AVFF assisted by experimental characterization	Secondary	from SAMOA project	WP2-task 2.2, WP3_task 3.1		lightweighting keeping unchanged the flexural behavior	Development of AVFF-based solution for the crash front end subgroup, and the extension of the concept throughout the body and chassis

Alessio Tommasi, GEM, alessio.tommasi@gemmate-technologies.com	AVFF elementary pattern virtual characterization of mechanical behaviour included crashworthiness	data about mechanical behaviour of elementary AVFF assisted by experimental characterization	Primary		WP2 and WP3	collected during the project	designing concept for lightweight and crash-tolerant structures	Development of AVFF-based solution for the crash front end subgroup, and the extension of the concept throughout the body and chassis
Francesco Bruzzo, Fraunhofer IWS, francesco.bruzzo@iws.fraunhofer.de	L-DED process parameters	List of L-DED process parameters and their impact on the material quality and geometrical accuracy	Primary	Laboratory generated data	WP2 - Task 2.1	End of task 2.1	L-DED process and material quality improvement	Development of AVFF-based solution for the crash front end subgroup, and the extension of the concept throughout the body and chassis
Alessio Gambi, IMC, alessio.gambi@fh-krems.ac.at	A Curated Set of Mixed-Traffic Critical Scenarios	In the dataset, we'll collect traces and scenario executions collected with the FLEXCRASH platform. The dataset will contain the description of the scenarios, the execution data (position, speed, etc.), and all the interactions of the human drivers and autonomous	Primary	The data would be generated by our platform starting from existing as well as newly generated traffic and critical scenarios	WP1 - Task 1.1, Task 1.2	A complete dataset will be released approximately by the end of 2 year. A revised dataset might be released by the end of the 3 year. The final dataset might be released by the end of the project. All the datasets will contain data	The dataset contains relevant scenarios that are either critical or relevant for testing and validation purposes. This dataset could be useful to developers of driving agents/ADAS/AV during development and validation.	Advanced materials models for crash modelling

		vehicles/driving agents involved in the mixed-traffic scenarios.				collected during the project.		
Begoña Casas; begona.casas@eurecat.org	Fracture toughness and fatigue data	Force-displacement data / S-N curves	Primary	Datasets from laboratory tests experiments	WP1- Task 2.3	All new data available in M28	To estimate material crashworthiness and durability in hybrid specimens and as input for virtual simulation. This data will be useful to select the best materials solutions in the project and in general for AM manufactures, parts producers.	Advancements in materials characterization for crashworthiness prediction/ Development of AVFF-based solution for the crash front end subgroup, and the extension of the concept throughout the body and chassis
Gestamp; Andoni Agirre; anagirre@gestamp.com	Full crash results	Full crash performance results of FLEXCRASH demonstrator	Primary	Results from crash simulations	WP1 - task 1.3 // WP4 - task 4.2	after the FLEXCRASH full crash simulation	The aim is to validate the designs done on a component basis by using a full vehicle model	Technical solution to improve the performances of the current aluminium extrusion profiles

Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH	Crash Performance Validation	Simulation Solver (LS-Dyna) Binary Data for virtual validation	Primary	Output data from simulation software	WP3 - Task 3.4	New Data finally ready in M40	Input data for crash performance and virtual testing methods, Task 3.4, Useful for Task Partners for further development	Advanced materials models for crash modelling
daniele pullini, CRF, daniele.pullini@crf.it	testing performance of a antiintrusion lateral door cross bar adopting the concept of AVFF	data and graphs	Secondary	From previous R&D project				Development of design concept for hybrid manufacturing
LTU (simon.jonsson@ltu.se)	Material characterisation data	Experimental results from material characterisation experiments	Primary	Internal code, Test equipment	WP1 - Task 1.4	After quasi-static and dynamic tensile testing in 1.4.2	To calibrate flow stress model developed in 1.4.1	Advancements in materials characterization for crashworthiness prediction
LTU (simon.jonsson@ltu.se)	Validation experiment data	Experimental data from component validation experiments	Primary	Test equipment	WP2 - Task 2.3	After advanced lab-scale testing in task 2.3	To validate material models developed in task 1.4	Advanced materials models for crash modelling

<p>LTU (simon.jonsson@ltu.se)</p>	<p>Model input files</p>	<p>Experimental data from component testing</p>	<p>Primary</p>	<p>Test equipment</p>	<p>WP3 - Task 3.3</p>	<p>M38</p>	<p>To test Flexcrash components in relevant loading conditions to prove concept and validate models</p>	<p>Flexcrash applied methods on improved prediction of crashworthiness allowing for virtual testing</p>
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1.Relevant partner:	Relation to project Result(s) – Why is this dataset relevant to the result(s) you selected? Add a short rationale for the result(s) you selected:	.Format / related standards / metadata: Provide details on the format	What is the Data sharing plan? Will you keep it open (e.g. submitted to an open repository), or closed, or will you license it?	If you have selected OPEN, please describe how it will be made available (e.g. submission to a repository ?)	Size / expected size (use a measurement unit that makes sense for the dataset):	FAIR DATA - Making data findable -Indicate how data are made identifiable, if a standard permanent identifier assignment scheme is used	FAIR DATA –Making data openly accessible Indicate ownership of the data -Indicate methods and SW tools needed to access the data. Clarify if the relevant software (e.g. in open source code) is i...	FAIR DATA –Making data interoperable Refer to commonly used ontologies to map the dataset, considering also the use of existing common platforms and tools	ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) and describe how you intend or might be able to cover these cost...
Míriam Vendrell Eurecat miriam.vendrell@eurecat.org	-The Social Media activity and publications help us to communicate relevant messages of the project and its main achievements	*.xml	Closed	NA	500kB	NA	Repositories Open for project's consortium through the SharePoint folder. Eurecat will be the main responsible to manage these data	NA	NA

Miriam Vendrell Eurecat miriam.vendrell@eurecat.org	-The website is the main communication channel of the project and helps us to spread the word about Flexcrash and its work done and results achieved	*.xml	Closed		5MB	NA	The website analytics data will be available to all project's consortium through the SharePoint folder.	NA	Eurecat will manage these data.
Miriam Vendrell Eurecat miriam.vendrell@eurecat.org	-It is important to have a significant number of subscribers to facilitate a more direct and personal dissemination of the project	*.csv	Closed		5MB	NA	The list of subscribers is private due to GDPR criteria. Eurecat can have this list and share some of the public details with the projects if necessary	NA	NA
Miriam Vendrell Eurecat miriam.vendrell@eurecat.org	-The communication and dissemination data help us to know the efficiency of these activities	*.xml	Closed		5MB	NA	SELFY repository (SHAREPOINT) EUT internal repository. Data will be open to Flexcrash partners during the project execution.	NA	NA

Míriam Vendrell Eurecat miriam.vendrell@ eurecat.org	-To reach the impact -of Flexcrash in communication media outlets	*.xml	Closed		10MB	NA	Data is closed, will be stored in an internal database for managing media relations in the project (coming from EUT media database).	NA	NA
Míriam Vendrell Eurecat miriam.vendrell@ eurecat.org	-These data are -important to manage the participation of attendants into project events.	*.xml	Closed		10MB	NA	Data in this dataset will be closed to events organisers due to GDPR.	NA	NA
Natàlia Carmona, Eurecat, natalia.carmona@ eurecat.org	The collection of the exploitable results ensures the data needed to develop a exploitation strategy	csv	Closed		1-50MB		Confidential data by FLEXCRASH consortium	NA	NA
Alessio Tommasi, GEM, alessio.tommasi@ gemmate- technologies.com	it will be used as a starting point for AVFF design and component re- design with optimised crashworthiness	.doc, .xls, .jpg	Other		few MB	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.

Alessio Tommasi, GEM, alessio.tommasi@gemmate-technologies.com	see above	.doc, .xls, .jpg	Other						
Francesco Bruzzo, Fraunhofer IWS, francesco.bruzzo@iws.fraunhofer.de	Quality performance of AVFF manufactured by L-DED	excel document or .csv	Other	Results publication in scientific journals	1 MB	not applicable	not applicable	NA	NA
Alessio Gambi, IMC, alessio.gambi@fh-krems.ac.at	The dataset will be useful in the project to identify likely crash configurations of future scenarios (e.g., crash angle, velocity) to optimize the design of the active safety mechanisms.	The data will be exported as JSON files containing the description of scenarios' road layout and initial state (defining the driving tasks and planned routes) and the observed relevant metrics for all the	Open	We plan to follow standard practices for reproducible research: 1. describe the dataset, its format, and intended usage in a peer-reviewed paper; and 2) released the dataset as "permanent	The expected size of the dataset is estimated as 200 scenario executions and about 1GB of data	We plan to release the data using Zenodo which will make it identifiable via a DOI. Keywords, indexing and tagging will follow the ACM Computing Classificat	Data will be exported in standard format (i.e., JSON) and the relevant software to visualize them (written in Python) will be released within the dataset.	There will be no restriction to use the data besides referencing the original paper describing it. We will adopt an open licensing mode (e.g., LGPL).	Alessio Gambi and his research group will be responsible to collect and manage the data. Since costs cannot be covered by IMC outside the scope of the project, we expect part of the costs to be covered within the allocated budget of the project and part of the data will be managed in according to availability (e.g., "best-effort")

		participants (position, speed, acceleration , rotation, etc.)		" artifiat identified with a DOI (e.g., using Zenodo)		ion System (https://doi.org/ 10.26434/chemrxiv-2023-12345)			
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<p>Begoña Casas; begona.casas@eu-recat.org</p>	<p>The generated data will be used to design materials with improved fracture and fatigue behaviour and as input for predictive models</p>	<p>CSV / XML</p>	<p>Open</p>	<p>Via project repository</p>			<p>No restrictions to re-use the data (only the permission of the materials producers)</p>	<p>Confidentiality agreements</p>	<p>None</p>
<p>Gestamp; Andoni Agirre; anagirre@gestamp.com</p>	<p>This dataset will confirm the advantages of the new technical solution to improve aluminum extrusion profiles</p>	<p>.xlsx / .pdf / .gif</p>	<p>Open</p>	<p>Via project repository</p>					

Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH	Relevant for the validation of different structure and load cases	virtual crash.txt, d3plot	.Closed		Up to 10GB, Output data size is customizable				
daniele pullini, CRF, daniele.pullini@crf.it	circumscribe the suitable geometry of AVFF on longitudinal flexural stiffness and deformation		Closed		unit of MB			data are under dissemination to public (scientific publication)	
LTU (simon.jonsson@ltu.se)	Applying method to bulk material	SMM Comma Separated Values (*.csv)	Closed		~ 10 MB	-	-	-	None
LTU (simon.jonsson@ltu.se)	3D DIC and high-speed cameras used to track the entire deformation process during impact will make model validation easier.	Portable Network Graphic (*.png), Comma Separated Values (*.csv), MPEG-4 (*.mp4)	Closed		~100 MB	-	-	-	None

LTU (simon.jonsson@ltu.se)	Proof of concept and model validation	and Portable Network Graphic (*.png), Comma Separated Values (*.csv), MPEG-4 (*.mp4)	Closed							
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